

Sentiment Analysis on MyPertamina Application Reviews Using NBC and SVM with Negation Handling

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ABSTRACT: Pertamina has issued a cashless application for fuel purchases since July 2019, named as MyPertamina. The application aims to make it easier for customers to make payments in transactions at fuel stations. MyPertamina application can currently be downloaded on Google Play Store. Since its release until now, MyPertamina has been downloaded as many as 10 million with a rating of 3.1 and 339 thousand reviews. Unfortunately, the low rating and user reviews dominated by negative comments show that the app's performance is still not satisfactory. The reviews data can be converted into valuable information by using sentiment analysis. Many researchers have applied sentiment analysis to MyPertamina user comment data. However, there have been no studies that apply the handling of negation in MyPertamina reviews, even though negative comments are very often found, i.e. 'tidak', 'jangan', 'belum' and 'bukan'. The negative words will change the sentiment of next sentence. Untreated negation words will lead to errors in classification which in turn will decrease accuracy. This study applies the handling of negation words using First Sentiment Word (FSW) and Fixed Window Length (FWL) methods. The classification algorithms used are Naïve Bayes Classifier (NBC) and Support Vector Machine (SVM). In this work, we analyzed 1000 comments consisting of 390 positive comments and 610 negative comments. The results showed that the best performance of negation handling is FSW. This method has improved accuracy by 2.5% and improved F1 by 1.5% using NBC algorithm and has improved accuracy by 2.9% and F1 by 3.4% using SVM algorithm.

KEYWORDS: negation handling, MyPertamina, NBC, SVM

1. INTRODUCTION

Every company today is required to utilize information technology in improving service to customers. As a State-Owned Enterprise Pertamina developed a non-cash fuel payment service, called MyPertamina. MyPertamina is a digital financial service application that is integrated with the LinkAja application. To get a MyPertamina account, users can download the application first from the Google Play Store (for Android phones) or App Store (for iPhone). The breakthrough app is intended to provide a convenient way for customers to transact [1]. This application also provides prizes in the form of earning points and redeeming points [2]. To support government policies in the distribution of fuel oil, this application is also intended to control the distribution of subsidized fuel to be right on target [3]. However, since it was first created on July 1, 2022, this application has encountered several obstacles so that many users are disappointed [4]. Complaints submitted by many users include the number of bugs, difficulty in registration, authentication and smoothness in use [5], and many officials lack understanding of the use of the system [6]. Currently, the MyPertamina application on Google Play store has a rating of 3.1 with 339 thousand reviews and has been downloaded by around 10 million users. The number of downloads is still far from the potential of motorized vehicle users, which is around 140 million [7].

However, the number of reviews can be elaborated further to determine the direction of the sentiment revealed from users, whether positive, negative or neutral. The study will use sentiment analysis to evaluate reviews in order to improve the system.

Sentiment analysis is the processing of text data that aims to analyze, process, extract textual data in the form of responses to an object or event and determine whether user sentiment includes positive and negative sentiments [8]. Sentiment analysis has been applied by many researchers on the MyPertamina application, among others, by [2], [9]-[10] and [11]. However, most sentiment analysis accuracy is still about 60%. This may be due to almost all researchers have not included negation handling factors in their analysis. According to [12] one of the causes of low accuracy in sentiment analysis is the absence of semantic analysis. Without semantic analysis, the ambiguity of meaning arising from negative words will cause the classification to be wrong. For example, on sentences "*aplikasi sangat tidak bagus*" which has a negative sentiment, because the tokenization process generally uses unigram units, the word "tidak" will be ignored so that sentiment will turn into positive sentiment. In fact, in the comments of MyPertamina users who tend to be negative, the percentage of the emergence of negation words such as: "tidak", "bukan", and "belum" tends to be very high. For that

reason, the handling of the word negation is indispensable in improving sentiment analysis performance. This study aims to apply the technique of handling the word negation in sentiment analysis. It is expected that with the application of negation word handling, the accuracy of sentiment analysis can be improved.

MyPertamina currently has a rating of 3.1 and product reviews of 339 thousand. The large number of reviews and low ratings have encouraged researchers to apply sentiment analysis to myPertamina reviews. The application of sentiment analysis in MyPertamina application product reviews has been widely carried out. Some researchers apply the NBC classification method, including [2], [10] and [11]. Setya Ananto & Hasan [2] analyzed 1.289 data with 285 positive data and 1004 negative data. The classification results obtained 77.4% accuracy, 49.9% precision and 76.8% recall. Nabilla et al. [9] conducted an analysis on 1001 *tweet* data sourced from twitter consisting of 494 positive and 507 negative. The results of the classification with NBC get 71% accuracy. The study with the more number of reviews data was [11] that used 3948 data, and [10] that used 5.722 data. The studies with the highest data reviews are [13] that used 8000 data with details of 4300 negatives, 1575 neutrals and 1325 positives. The latter uses the SVM method to perform classification. However, the analysis results only showed 67% accuracy, 69% recall and 57% precision. It can be seen from the algorithm used by the researchers mostly using NBC and SVM. According to the [14] NBC method, it is the fastest method compared to other classification methods.

The application of negation handling in sentiment analysis has been widely done by researchers on various text and various languages, including dutch [15] and english [16]. The increasing number of text reviews in Indonesian has encouraged researchers to study the importance of handling negation for sentiment analysis on Indonesian objects. Ramadhan et al. (2022) have applied negation handling to Covid-19 data collected from Twitter as many as 902 data (441 positive, 195 negative and 266 neutral). The results showed a slight increase in accuracy from 59.1% to 59.6%. Another negation handling study on Twitter was conducted by [18] has increased accuracy by about 3.17%. Implementation of negation handling by using modified syntactic rule have been done by [19]. By applying their method to 1000 hotel review data (500 positive and 500 negative) they got an increase in accuracy of 3,3%.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted through 3 stages, namely data collection, pre-processing and data analysis. The flowchart of the research process is presented in Figure1.

2.1 Data Collection

The data used in this research was crawled from MyPertamina user reviews posted on Google Play Store. The collected data still contains unnecessary data, such as id-user, date of posting, photo caption, etc. **Data cleaning** is meant to

remove unnecessary information so that only comments are left that will be processed in the next step. Dataset used Indonesian Language that have been labelled as positive and negative. The **data labelling** process applies a lexicon-based algorithm. The list of lexicons used is 10,218 lexicons consisting of 3.609 positive lexicons and 6.609 negative lexicons [20]. From the positive lexicons and negative lexicon we selects only lexicons that come from a single word.

Figure 1. Flowchart of Research Steps

2.2 Preprocessing

Preprocessing is very important in sentiment analysis, because preprocessing turning raw data into clean data that ready for sentiment analysis processes. The preprocessing steps consist of:

- 1) *Case folding* : Because not all text documents are letter-consistent, this process change the letter characters in the comment to all lowercase characters.
- 2) *Filtering* : In this process adjustments are made by removing special characters such oter characters (\$,%,* and so on). This process also eliminates words that do not match the parsed results. For example usernames that start with the symbol “@” or hashtags “#”.
- 3) *Tokenizing* : Tokenizing process break the review down into word units. The tokenizing process is carried out by looking at every space in the review. Based on these spaces the words can be separated.
- 4) *Normalization* : The process of converting non-standard words into standard words. For example the words ‘nggak’, ‘tdk’ will be converted into ‘tidak’, the word ‘dpt’ will converted into ‘dapat’.
- 5) *Stopword removal* : Stopword is a word that appears frequently and has no informational value because it cannot distinguish documents, such as ‘ini’, ‘yang’, ‘dari’, ‘ke’ etc. This stage serves to eliminate words that have no influence in the later classification process.
- 6) *Stemming*: This step converts the word to its root word with the goal of lowering the dimensionality of the words in the collection.

2.3 TF-IDF

TF-IDF is feature extraction technique to measure the weighting of words in a document. The measure called term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) is defined as $tf_{ij} * idf_i$, where tf_{ij} denote the number of occurrences of term t_i in document d_j , and idf_i denote the inverse document

frequency of term *i*. If **N** is the total number of documents in the collection and **idf_i** is the number of documents containing term *i*, then the **TF-IDF** weighting can be written as equation (1)[21].

$$w_{i,j} = tf_{ij} \times \log\left(\frac{N}{df_i}\right) \tag{1}$$

2.4 Data Labelling

The dataset taken from scrapping and cleaning process is still a raw data that does not yet have a target class, so it is necessary to label the dataset. The process of labeling document is done by lexicon based approach. We use a list of positive lexicons such as Table 1 and a list of negative lexicons such as Table 2.

For data labeling, 3 algorithms are used, namely lexicon-based labeling without negation, lexicon-based labeling with FSW method negation and labeling with FWL method negation. Algorithms are presented in algorithm 1, algorithm 2 and algorithm 3. This method detects the negation words in the text and reverses the sentiment of the word that follows it. For FSW we reverse the first word sentiment, while for FWL it reverses *n*'th sentiment word behind the negation word.

Table 1. Pos-Lexicon Library

Word	Sentiment weight
Puas	+1
Nyaman	+1
ok	+1
Lancer	+1
..	..
Hebat	+1

Table 2. Neg-Lexicon library

Word	Sentiment weight
Parah	-1
Payah	-1
Jelek	-1
Ribet	-1
..	..
Susah	-1

Algorithm 1 Find_Label_Of_Dokumen

Input : document , a list of *Pos_Lexicon_List*, *Neg_Lexicon_List*
: label of document

Output

```

1 Count_Pos=0; count_Neg=0;
2 foreach w in word_of_Doc_List do
3     If w in Pos_Lexicon_List do
4         count_Pos =count_Pos +1
5     else
6         If w in Neg_Lexicon_List do
```

```

7         count_Neg=count_Neg-1
8     endif
9     endif
10 If (count_Pos + count_Neg) > 0 do
11     return 'positive'
12 else
13     return 'negative'
```

Algorithm 2 Find_Label_Of_Dokumen_with_Negation_Handling_FSW

Input : document , *Pos_Lexicon_List*, *Neg_Lexicon_List*, *NEG_word_List*
: label of dokumen

Output

```

1 word_of_Doc_List =document.split() // split
dokumen into list
2 Count_Pos=0; count_Neg=0;
n=len(word_of_doc_List)
3 for i in rangen (n) do
4     If word_of_Doc_List[i] in NEG_word_List
do
5         If word_of_Doc_List[i+1] in
Pos_Lexicon_List do
6             count_Pos =count_Pos -1
7         Else
8             If word_of_Doc_List[i+1] in
Neg_Lexicon_List do
9                 count_Neg=count_Neg+1
10            endif
11        endif
12    If (count_Pos + count_Neg) > 0 do
13        return 'positive'
14    else
15        return 'negative'
```

Algorithm 3 Find_Label_Of_Dokumen_with_Negation_Handling_FWL

Input : document , *Pos_Lexicon_List*, *Neg_Lexicon_List*, *NEG_word_List*, *L*
Output : label of dokumen

```

1 word_of_Doc_List =document.split() // split
dokumen
into list
2 Count_Pos=0; count_Neg=0;
n=len(word_of_doc_List)
3 for i in rangen (n) do
4     If word_of_Doc_List[i] in NEG_word_List do
5     If word_of_Doc_List[i+L] in Pos_Lexicon_List do
6         count_Pos =count_Pos -1
7         Else
8     If word_of_Doc_List[i+L] in Neg_Lexicon_List do
```

```

9         count_Neg=count_Neg+1
10        endif
11        endif
12        If (count_Pos + count_Neg) > 0 do
13            return 'positive'
14        else
15            return 'negative'
16        endif
    
```

2.5 Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the classification algorithm, the confusion matrix is arranged as Table 3 :

Table 3. Confusion Matrix of classification results

		Actual Values	
		Positive	Negative
Predicted Values	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
	Negative	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

From the confusion matrix we derived various classification performance parameters, including:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \tag{2}$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{3}$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+TN+FN} \tag{4}$$

To compare the performance of two algorithms we combine Precision and Recall in one measure, namely as F1 formulated in equation (5). F1-score helps to measure Recall and Precision at the same time.

$$F1 = \frac{2*Precision*Recall}{Precision+Recall} \tag{5}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Preparing Dataset

The data collection process is carried out using scrapping techniques on the google play store (<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.dafturn.mypertamina>). The data taken in this study is part of consumer reviews and ratings. The code for scrapping process can be seen in Figure 2.

```

!pip install google-play-scraper
from google_play_scraper import
Sort, reviews
result, continuation_token=reviews('com.dafturn.mypertamina', lang='id', country='id', sort=Sort.NEWEST, count=1000, filter_score with=None)
    
```

Figure 2. Code for Scrapping Data

The data collected from scrapping is still contains attributes that may not be needed for data analysis, such as *reviewId*, *userName*, *userImage*, etc (see Table 4). For this

reason, a data cleaning process is needed so that only what we need is left, namely content. The program code to drop attributes that are not needed is as shown in Figure 3 below. Review data consisting of content is stored in a csv file as formatted in Table 5.

```

dataset.drop(['reviewId', 'userName', 'userImage', 'score', 'thumbsUpCount', 'reviewCreatedVersion', 'at', 'replyContent', 'replyAt', 'appVersion'])
    
```

Figure 3. Code for Dropping Unnecessary Attributes

Table 4. Sample of Original Dataset

reviewId	a1f9a3fe-9d7b-4136-b3c7-d091e36a718f
userName	Reffi Siregar
userImage	https://play-lh.googleusercontent.com/a-/ALV-UjVPU4YrdhJFoMahlt226mjn3B1nzZZRxAoQ3y3m-wq7U
content	Dah isi banyak dgn harapan point dapat banyak juga error sistemnya... Sama sekali ga bisa di akses... Kaya maen maen Tp sewaktu isi dikit ok ok aja ga ada masalah... Jadi kaya aneh gitu...
score	1
thumbsUpCount	0
reviewCreatedVersion	4.2.3
at	10/25/2023 3:54
replyContent	
repliedAt	
appVersion	4.2.3

Table 5. Sample of Dataset Save in CSV

No	reviews
1	Aplikasi bagus tapi banyak errornya
2	Dah isi banyak dgn harapan point dapat banyak juga error sistemnya... Sama sekali ga bisa di akses...
3	Update terossss lg dk kios malah nunggu update bangke
4	Program cukup bisa membantu
5	smoga beruntung mendapat hadiah.. tukar poin

After the application of the data labeling algorithm, we will get reviews that have been labeled. Examples of review that have been labeled are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Sentiment Review after Labelling

No	Reviews	Sentiment
1	Aplikasi bagus tapi banyak errornya	Negative
2	Dah isi banyak dgn harapan point dapat banyak juga error sistemnya... Sama sekali ga bisa di akses...	Negative
3	Update terossss lg dk kios malah nunggu update bangke	Negative
4	Program cukup bisa membantu	Positive
5	smoga beruntung mendapat hadiah.. tukar poin	poistive

The results of labeling data using three algorithm produce the following dataset (Table 7).

Table 7. Dataset for Classification

No	Reviews	Negative	Positive	Total
1	Without Negation Handling	398	602	1000
2	With Negation Handling FSW	390	610	1000
3	With Negation Handling FWLn=2	385	615	1000

3.2 Pre-Preprocessing

Pre-processing was done on datasets that have been labeled positive and negative using a lexicon-based algorithm. As an illustration if we have a review as follows:

“Aplikasi ribet bikin pusing, sdh lama pakai app ini dan sdh dpt kode QR...stelah di UPDATE malah suruh daftar ulang..GIMANA?!”

The preprocessing steps can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. The Preprocessing Step and Results

Preprocessing step	Results
Casefolding	aplikasi ribet bikin pusing, sdh lama pake app ini dan sdh dpt kode qr...stelah diupdate malah disuruh daftar ulang..gimana?!
Filtering	aplikasi ribet bikin pusing sdh lama pake app ini dan sdh dpt kode qr stelah diupdate malah disuruh daftar ulang gimana
Tokenizing	[aplikasi],[ribet],[bikin],[pusing],[sdh],[lama], [pake], [app], [ini], [dan], [sdh], [dpt],[kode],[qr],[stelah],[diupdate],[malah],[disuruh], [daftar], [ulang],[gimana]
Normalization	[aplikasi],[ribet],[bikin],[pusing],[sudah],[lama], [pakai], [app], [ini], [dan], [sudah],[dapat],[kode],[qr],[setelah],[diupdate],[malah],[disuruh], [daftar], [ulang],[gimana]

Stopword Removal	[aplikasi],[ribet],[bikin],[pusing],[lama],[pakai],[app],[dapat],[kode],[qr],[update],[malah], [disuruh], [daftar], [ulang],[gimana]
Stemming	[aplikasi],[ribet],[bikin],[pusing],[lama],[pakai],[app],[dapat],[kode],[qr],[update],[malah], [suruh], [daftar], [ulang],[gimana]

The final step in Pre-processing is to compile a list of tokens for all documents in training. Furthermore, from the list of tokens, a term document matrix is created that records the frequency of occurrence of terms in the document. The TF document-term matrix is presented in Table 9. From Matrix TF, we converted into normalized TF-IDF matrix in Table 10. This final matrix is then ready to be classify using NBC and SVM algorithm.

Table 9. TF-IDF Weighting of Document

Doc	a	s	b	r	o	b	d	p	...	s	class
	p	a	a	i	k	b	a	u		u	
	l	n	n	b		m	f	s		l	
	i	g	t	e			t	i		i	
	k	a	u	t			a	n		t	
	a	t					r	g			
	s										
	i										
Doc-1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1
Doc-2	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	-1
Doc-3	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	-1
...											
Doc-n	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	+1

Table 10. Normalized TF-IDF Weighting of Document

Doc	a	s	b	r	o	b	d	p	...	s	class
	p	a	a	i	k	b	a	u		u	
	l	n	n	b		m	f	s		l	
	i	g	t	e			t	i		i	
	k	a	u	t			a	n		t	
	a	t					r	g			
	s										
	i										
Doc-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1
	.5	.5	.5								
	.7	.7	.7								
	.7	.7	.7								
	.5	.5									
Doc-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
	.6			.3						.3	
	.2									.1	

	2			1						1	
	0			1						0	
Doc-3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
				.			.	.			
				4			4	4			
				2			2	2			
				2			2	2			
								3			
...											
Doc-n	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	+1
			
	7			7							
	0			0							
				7							

	7									
	1									

2. 3 Analysis and Evaluation

Classification is carried out using two classification methods, namely the NBC and SVM methods. The classification results are the result of various combinations of training data and testing data, namely a combination of training:testing, i.e 60:40, 70:30, 80:20, and 90:10. Each combination will produce a confusion matrix from which evaluation parameters are set, namely precision, recall, accuracy and F1 value. Table 11 shows the comparison of performance between Non Negation Handling and With Negation Handling (FSW) for NBC algorithm. A comparison of the FWL algorithm with classification using NBC is presented in Table 12 for n=2 and n=3.

Table 11. Comparison of Algorithm Performance (NBC)

Combination Training:Testing	Without Negation Handling				With Negation Handling FSW			
	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1
60:40	67.2%	68.4%	62.5%	67.8%	69.4%	63.8%	64.8%	66.5%
70:30	68.3%	65.2%	63.7%	66.7%	69.7%	67.8%	65.5%	68.7%
80:20	68.2%	67.2%	65.6%	66.7%	69.2%	67.2%	68.1%	68.2%
90:10	64.7%	65.7%	64.1%	65.2%	65.6%	66.8%	66.7%	66.2%

Table 12. Comparison of Algorithm Performance (NBC) Using FWL

Combination Training:Testing	With Negation Handling FWL n=2				With Negation Handling FWL n=3			
	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1
60:40	65.3%	66.2%	61.5%	65.7%	64.2%	64.2%	62.3%	64.2%
70:30	67.2%	65.3%	64.3%	66.2%	65.2%	66.3%	63.4%	65.7%
80:20	67.7%	64.3%	65.8%	66.0%	66.2%	61.2%	64.3%	63.6%
90:10	63.2%	64.5%	63.8%	63.8%	59.5%	63.2%	66.7%	61.3%

SVM classification performance is presented in Table 13 and Table 14 for comparison without Negation handling and with

negation handling (FSW) and comparison between negation handling FWL with n=2 and n=3

Table 13. Comparison of Algorithm Performance (SVM)

Combination Training:Testing	Without Negation Handling				With Negation Handling FSW			
	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1
60:40	69.1%	67.9%	69.4%	68.5%	72.3%	70.2%	64.8%	71.2%
70:30	71.2%	68.3%	70.3%	69.7%	71.3%	73.2%	65.5%	72.2%
80:20	72.3%	70.4%	72.3%	71.3%	74.3%	75.1%	75.2%	74.7%
90:10	67.2%	66.5%	67.4%	66.8%	65.6%	68.5%	71.2%	67.0%

Table 14. Comparison of Algorithm Performance (SVM) Using FWL

Combination Training:Testing	With Negation Handling FWL n=2				With Negation Handling FWL n=3			
	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1	Precision	Recall	Accuracy	F1
60:40	70.2%	61.5%	69.8%	67.8%	66.8%	62.3%	67.3%	70.2%
70:30	68.3%	64.3%	69.2%	68.2%	67.3%	63.1%	67.7%	68.3%
80:20	69.3%	65.8%	70.2%	69.3%	68.2%	64.3%	68.7%	69.3%
90:10	66.4%	63.8%	67.3%	65.2%	63.2%	66.7%	64.2%	66.4%

It can be seen from Table 11, Table 12, Table 13 and Table 14 that the parameter will reach a maximum mostly in combinations of 80:20. Therefore, we take a summary of the

comparison of accuracy and F1 from a combination of 80:20. The results are as in table 12.

Table 15. Summary Comparison of Classification Performance

Dataset	NBC		SVM	
	Accuracy	F1	Accuracy	F1
Without Negation Handling	65.6%	66.7%	72.3%	71.3%
With Negation Handling FSW	68.1%	68.2%	75.2%	74.7%
With Negation Handling FWL n=2	65.8%	66.0%	70.2%	69.3%
With Negation Handling FWL n=3	64.3%	63.6%	68.7%	69.3%

From table 15 we concluded that the application of negation handling has increased the classification performance, both NBC and SVM algorithms. The NBC algorithm has increased accuracy by 2.5% and F1 by 1.5%, while the SVM algorithm has increased accuracy by 2.9 and increased F1 by 3.4%.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of this study is that negation handling has been able to increase the performance of the classification algorithm, either FSW or FWL. In the application of the FWL algorithm, the use of n=2 results in better performance compared to n=3. In general, the performance parameters of the FWL method are still less than the FSW method. Compared with classification without negation handling, the NBC algorithm has increased accuracy by 2.5% and F1 by 1.5%, while the SVM algorithm has increased accuracy by 2.9% and increased F1 by 3.4%.

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